

The Mathematics Education
Volume-LIX, No. 3, September 2025

ISSN 0047-6269

Journal website: <https://internationaljournalsiwan.com/Mathematic.php>

ORCID Link: <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-7467-6080>

International Impact Factor: 7.75 <https://impactfactorservice.com/home/journal/2295>

Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?hl=en&user=UOfM8B4AAAAJ>

Refereed and Peer-Reviewed Quarterly Journal

Fixed Point Result of Reich Type Contraction on Controlled Metric Spaces

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(Received: August 29, 2025; Accepted: September 15, 2025;
Published Online: September 30, 2025)

Abstract:

In this paper, we present a new fixed point result for Reich type Contractions in the setting of generalized controlled metric space with three control functions.

Keywords: Controlled metric space, Double controlled metric space, Reich type contraction.

1. Introduction:

Fixed point theory has numerous applications in science and engineering. The proof of existence and uniqueness theorems for solutions of ordinary and boundary value problems often rely on the application of various fixed point

[34]

theorems. Among them, the Banach contraction principle is the most widely used, and it has been extensively generalized by modifying the contractive condition or by extending the underlying metric space. Kamran et al. [1] originate the theory of an extended b -metric space. Mlaiki et al. [2] originate the theory of a controlled metric space. Abdeljawad et al. [3] further extended this idea by addressing the double controlled metric space, while Tasneem et al. [4] advanced the theory by defining a triple controlled metric space. Singh et al. [5] originate a generalization of the controlled metric space by integrating three control functions. In this paper, we present a new fixed point theorem for Reich type Contractions in the setting of generalized controlled metric space with three control functions. These result, generalisation of pre existing results of Singh et al. [5] and others.

2. Preliminaries:

Definition 2.1 [1]: Let $Z \neq \Phi$, $d : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a non-negative function and $\alpha : Z \times Z \rightarrow [1, \infty)$ be control functions satisfying the following conditions:

- I. $d(f, g) = 0$ if and only if $f = g$,
- II. $d(f, g) = d(g, f)$
- III. $d(f, g) \leq \alpha(f, g) [d(f, h) + d(h, g)] \quad \forall f, g, h \in Z$.

Then d is called a extended b -metric and (Z, d) is a extended b -metric space.

Definition 2.2 [2]: Let $Z \neq \Phi$, $d : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a non-negative function and $\alpha : Z \times Z \rightarrow [1, \infty)$ be control functions satisfying the following conditions:

- I. $d(f, g) = 0$ if and only if $f = g$,
- II. $d(f, g) = d(g, f)$
- III. $d(f, g) \leq \alpha(f, h) d(f, h) + \alpha(h, g) d(h, g) \quad \forall f, g, h \in Z$.

Then d is called a controlled metric and (Z, d) is a controlled metric space.

Example 2.3 [2]: Let $Z = [0, \infty)$ and a function define by $d : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ such that

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(f, g) &= 0 \text{ if } f = g, \\
 &= \frac{1}{f}, \text{ if } f \text{ is even and } g \text{ is odd,} \\
 &= \frac{1}{g}, \text{ if } f \text{ is odd and } g \text{ is even,} \\
 &= 1, \text{ otherwise,}
 \end{aligned}$$

and the controlled function $\alpha : Z \times Z \rightarrow [1, \infty)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \alpha(f, g) &= f, \text{ if } f \text{ is even and } g \text{ is odd,} \\
 &= g, \text{ if } f \text{ is odd and } g \text{ is odd,} \\
 &= 1, \text{ otherwise.}
 \end{aligned}$$

Then d is called a controlled metric and (Z, d) is a controlled metric space.

Definition 2.4 [3]: Let $Z \neq \Phi$, $d : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a non-negative function and $\alpha, \beta : Z \times Z \rightarrow [1, \infty)$ be two control functions satisfying the following conditions:

- I. $d(f, g) = 0$ if and only if $f = g$,
- II. $d(f, g) = d(g, f)$,
- III. $d(f, g) \leq \alpha(f, h) d(f, h) + \beta(h, g) d(h, g) \quad \forall f, g, h \in Z$.

Then d is called a double controlled metric and (Z, d) is a double controlled metric space.

Example 2.5 [3]: Let $Z = [0, \infty)$ and a function define by $d : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ such that

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(f, g) &= 0 \text{ if } x = y, \\
 &= \frac{1}{f}, \text{ if } f \geq 1 \text{ and } g \in [0, 1) \\
 &= \frac{1}{g}, \text{ if } g \geq 1 \text{ and } f \in [0, 1) \\
 &= 1, \text{ otherwise}
 \end{aligned}$$

and the controlled functions $\alpha, \beta : Z \times Z \rightarrow [1, \infty)$ by

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha(f, g) &= f, \text{ if } f, g \geq 1 \\ &= 1, \text{ otherwise} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \beta(f, g) &= 1, \text{ if } f, g < 1 \\ &= \max \{f, g\}, \text{ otherwise.} \end{aligned}$$

Then d is called a double controlled metric and (Z, d) is a double controlled metric space.

Singh et al. introduce a generalization of the controlled metric space by introducing three control functions.

Definition 2.6 [5]: Let $Z \neq \Phi$, $d : Z \times Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a non-negative function and $\alpha, \beta, \gamma : Z \times Z \times Z \rightarrow [1, \infty)$ be three control functions satisfying the following conditions:

- I. $d(f, g, h) = 0$ if at least two of the three points are the same.
- II. For $f, g \in Z$ such that $f \neq g$ there exist a point $h \in Z$ such that $d(f, g, h) \neq 0$.
- III. For $f, g, h \in Z$, $d(f, g, h) = d(f, h, g) = d(g, h, f) = d(h, f, g) = d(g, f, h) = d(h, g, f)$
- IV. For $f, g, h, a \in Z$, $d(f, g, h) \leq \alpha(f, g, a) d(f, g, a) + \beta(g, h, a) d(g, h, a) + \gamma(h, f, a) d(h, f, a)$.

Then d is called controlled metric and (Z, d) is a controlled metric space.

Example 2.7: Let $Z = (0, 1)$ and $d : Z \times Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} d(f, g, h) &= 0, \text{ if at least two of the three points are the same.} \\ &= \mu(f, g, h) e^{1/2|f-g|+3/8|g-h|+1/8|h-f|} \text{ otherwise.} \end{aligned}$$

For continuous $\alpha(f, g, h) \geq 0$ symmetric in f, g, h . It suffices to only verify property (IV) of definition 2.6. Which typically in such generalized setting takes a form like.

For all $f, g, h, t \in Z$.

$$d(f, g, h) = \alpha(f, g, t) d(f, g, t) + \beta(g, h, t) d(g, h, t) + \gamma(h, f, t) d(h, f, t)$$

for some control function $\alpha, \beta, \gamma : Z \times Z \times Z \rightarrow [1, \infty)$.

Using Jensen's inequality applied of the convex function $f(x) = e^x$ along with modulus power $|a|$.

$$\begin{aligned} d(f, g, h) &= \mu(f, g, h) e^{1/2|f-g|+3/8|g-h|+1/8|h-f|} \\ &\leq \mu(f, g, h) \left[\frac{1}{2} e^{|f-g|} + \frac{3}{8} e^{|g-h|} + \frac{1}{8} e^{|h-f|} \right] \\ &= \mu(f, g, h) \left[\frac{1}{2} e^{1/2|f-g|+1/2|f-g|} + \frac{3}{8} e^{1/2|g-h|+1/2|g-h|} + \frac{1}{8} e^{1/2|h-f|+1/2|h-f|} \right] \\ &\leq \left[\frac{1}{2} e^{1/2|f-g|} + 1 \right] \mu(f, g, h) e^{1/2|f-g|+3/8|g-t|+1/8|t-f|} \\ &\quad + \left[\frac{3}{8} e^{1/2|h-g|} + 1 \right] \mu(f, g, h) e^{1/2|h-g|+3/8|g-t|+1/8|t-h|} \\ &\quad + \left[\frac{1}{8} e^{1/2|h-f|} + 1 \right] \mu(f, g, h) e^{1/2|h-f|+3/8|f-t|+1/8|t-h|} \\ &= \alpha(f, g, t) d(f, g, t) + \beta(g, h, t) d(h, g, t) + \gamma(h, f, t) d(h, f, t) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Where } \alpha(f, g, t) = \frac{1}{2} e^{1/2|f-g|} + 1 \geq 1$$

$$\beta(g, h, t) = \frac{3}{8} e^{1/2|g-h|} + 1 \geq 1$$

$$\gamma(h, f, t) = \frac{1}{8} e^{1/2|h-f|} + 1 \geq 1.$$

Definition 2.8 [5]: Let (Z, d) be a controlled metric space. Let $H : Z \rightarrow Z$ we say H is continuous at the pair $(a, b) \in Z \times Z$ if for every $\epsilon > 0$, there exist $r > 0$ such that

$$H(B_r(f, g)) \circ B_c(f, g).$$

Definition 2.9 [5]: Let (Z, d) be a controlled metric-type space.

- I. The sequence $\{f_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ converges to $f \in Z$. If for every $\epsilon > 0$, there exists an integer $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $n \geq N$. $d(f_n, f, t) < \epsilon$ for some fixed $t \in Z$.
- II. The sequence $\{f_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a Cauchy sequence. If for every $\epsilon > 0$, there exist an integer $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $n, m \geq N$. $d(f_n, f_m, t) < \epsilon$ for some fixed $t \in Z$.
- III. The space (Z, d) is complete, if every Cauchy sequence in Z is convergent.

In order to simplify results, we define the following products as follows:

Define

$$U_0(t, f_n, f_{n+1}) = \alpha$$

$$U_1(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}) = \beta\gamma$$

$$U_2(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}, f_{n+3}) = \beta\alpha\gamma$$

$$U_3(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}, f_{n+3}, f_{n+4}) = \beta\alpha\alpha\gamma$$

In general

$$U_{m-n-1}(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}, f_{n+3}, f_{n+4}, \dots, f_{m-1}) = \beta(\alpha \dots (m-n-2) \text{ times}) \gamma$$

Define

$$V_0(t, f_n, f_m) = \gamma$$

$$V_1(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}) = \beta\beta$$

$$V_2(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}, f_{n+3}) = \beta\alpha\beta$$

$$V_3(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}, f_{n+3}, f_{n+4}) = \beta\alpha\alpha\beta$$

In general

$$V_{m-n-1}(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}, f_{n+3}, f_{n+4}, \dots, f_{m-1}) = \beta(\alpha \dots (m-n-2) \text{ times}) \beta$$

3. Main Results:

Theorem 3.1: Let $Z \neq \Phi$ and (Z, d) be a complete controlled metric space. Let $H : Z \rightarrow Z$ be a functions subject to the Reich contraction

$$(3.1) \quad d(Hf, Hg, t) \leq a d(f, g, t) + b d(f, Hf, t) + c d(g, Hg, t) \quad \forall f, g, t \in Z \text{ and} \\ a + b + c < 1.$$

Assume that

$$(3.2) \quad \sup_{m \geq 1} \lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{(a+b)}{(1-c)} U_{j+1}(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, \dots, f_{j+2}) / U_j(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, \dots, f_{j+1}) \right| < 1$$

$$(3.3) \quad \sup_{m \geq 1} \lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{(a+b)}{(1-c)} V_{j+1}(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, \dots, f_{j+2}) / V_j(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, \dots, f_{j+1}) \right| < 1$$

Also assume that for each $f \in Z$, the limits

$$(3.4) \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha(f, f_n, t), \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \beta(f, f_n, t) \text{ and } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \gamma(f, f_n, t) \text{ exists.}$$

Then H has a unique fixed point in Z .

Proof: Let $f_0 \in Z$ be arbitrary. Define sequence $\{f_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ by $f_{n+1} = Hf_n$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then from (3.1), we get

$$d(f_n, f_{n+1}, t) = d(Hf_{n-1}, Hf_n, t) \leq a d(f_{n-1}, f_n, t) + b d(f_{n-1}, Hf_{n-1}, t) + c d(f_n, Hf_n, t) \\ = a d(f_{n-1}, f_n, t) + b d(f_{n-1}, f_n, t) + c d(f_n, f_{n+1}, t)$$

$$(1-c) d(f_n, f_{n+1}, t) \leq (a+b) d(f_{n-1}, f_n, t)$$

$$d(f_n, f_{n+1}, t) \leq \frac{(a+b)}{(1-c)} d(f_{n-1}, f_n, t)$$

$$(a+b)/(1-c) < 1$$

$$(3.5) \quad d(f_n, f_{n+1}, t) \leq \frac{(a+b)}{(1-c)} d(f_{n-1}, f_n, t) \text{ for all } n \geq n_0$$

By recursion

$$(3.6) \quad d(f_n, f_{n+1}, a) \leq \left[\frac{(a+b)}{(1-c)} \right]^n d(f_0, f_1, t) \text{ for all } n \geq n_0$$

Showing Cauchy Property:

Let $m, n \in N$ with $m > n$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(f_n, f_m, t) &\leq \alpha(f_n, f_m, f_{n+1}) d(f_n, f_m, f_{n+1}) + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+2}) d(f_m, t, f_{n+2}) \\
 &\quad + \gamma(t, f_n, f_{n+1}) d(t, f_n, f_{n+1}) \\
 &\leq \alpha(f_n, f_m, f_{n+1}) d(f_n, f_m, f_{n+1}) + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \alpha(f_n, f_m, f_{n+1}) d(f_n, f_m, f_{n+1}) \\
 &\quad + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \beta(t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}) d(t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}) + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \\
 &\quad \gamma(f_{n+1}, f_m, f_{n+2}) d(f_{n+1}, f_m, f_{n+2}) + \gamma(t, f_n, f_{n+1}) d(t, f_n, f_{n+1}) \\
 &\leq \alpha(f_n, f_m, f_{n+1}) d(f_n, f_m, f_{n+1}) + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+2}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+3}) \\
 &\quad d(f_m, t, f_{n+3}) + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+2}) \beta(t, f_{n+2}, f_{n+3}) d(t, f_{n+2}, f_{n+3}) \\
 &\quad + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+2}) \gamma(f_{n+2}, f_m, f_{n+3}) d(f_{n+2}, f_m, f_{n+3}) \\
 &\quad + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \beta(t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}) d(t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}) + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \\
 &\quad \gamma(f_{n+1}, f_m, f_{n+2}) d(f_{n+1}, f_m, f_{n+2}) + \gamma(t, f_n, f_{n+1}) d(t, f_n, f_{n+1}) \\
 d(f_n, f_m, t) &\leq \alpha(f_n, f_m, f_{n+1}) d(f_n, f_m, f_{n+1}) + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+2}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+3}) \\
 &\quad \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+4}) d(f_m, t, f_{n+4}) \\
 &\quad + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+2}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+3}) \beta(t, f_{n+3}, f_{n+4}) d(t, f_{n+3}, f_{n+4}) \\
 &\quad + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+2}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+3}) \gamma(f_{n+3}, f_m, f_{n+4}) d(f_{n+3}, f_m, f_{n+4}) \\
 &\quad + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+2}) \beta(t, f_{n+2}, f_{n+3}) d(t, f_m, f_{n+3}) \\
 (3.7) \quad &\quad + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+2}) \gamma(f_{n+2}, f_m, f_{n+3}) d(f_{n+2}, f_m, f_{n+3}) \\
 &\quad + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \beta(t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}) d(t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}) \\
 &\quad + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \gamma(f_{n+1}, f_m, f_{n+2}) d(f_{n+1}, f_m, f_{n+2}) \\
 &\quad + \gamma(t, f_n, f_{n+1}) d(t, f_n, f_{n+1})
 \end{aligned}$$

Using 3.6, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(f_n, f_m, t) &\leq \alpha(f_n, f_m, f_{n+1})k^n d(f_0, f_m, f_1) + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+2}) \\
 &\quad \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+3}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+4}) d(f_m, t, f_{n+4}) \\
 &\quad + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+2}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+3}) \beta(t, f_{n+3}, f_{n+4})k^{n+3} d(t, f_0, f_1) \\
 &\quad + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+2}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+3}) \gamma(f_{n+3}, f_m, f_{n+4})k^{n+3} d(f_0, f_m, f_1) \\
 &\quad + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+2}) \beta(t, f_{n+2}, f_{n+3})k^{n+2} d(t, f_0, f_1) \\
 (3.8) \quad &\quad + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \alpha(f_m, t, f_{n+2}) \gamma(f_{n+2}, f_m, f_{n+3})k^{n+2} d(f_0, f_m, f_1) \\
 &\quad + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \beta(t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2})k^{n+1} d(t, f_0, f_1) \\
 &\quad + \beta(f_m, t, f_{n+1}) \gamma(f_{n+1}, f_m, f_{n+2})k^{n+1} d(f_0, f_m, f_1) \\
 &\quad + \gamma(t, f_m, f_{n+1})k^n d(t, f_0, f_1).
 \end{aligned}$$

It follows that inequality, (3.8), can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(f_n, f_m, t) &\leq \left[\frac{(a+b)}{(1-c)} \right]^n d(f_0, f_1, f_m) \left[U_0(f_n, f_m, f_{n+1}) \right. \\
 &\quad + \left[\frac{(a+b)}{(1-c)} \right] U_1(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}) + \left[\frac{(a+b)}{(1-c)} \right]^2 U_2(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}, f_{n+3}) + \dots \\
 &\quad \left. + \left[\frac{(a+b)}{(1-c)} \right]^{m-n-1} U_{m-n-1}(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}, \dots, f_{m-1} \dots) \right] \\
 (3.9) \quad &\quad + \left[\frac{(a+b)}{(1-c)} \right]^n d(f_0, f_1, t) \left[V_0(f_n, f_m, f_{n+1}) \right. \\
 &\quad + \left[\frac{(a+b)}{(1-c)} \right] V_1(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}) + \left[\frac{(a+b)}{(1-c)} \right]^2 V_2(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}, f_{n+3}) + \dots \\
 &\quad \left. + \left[\frac{(a+b)}{(1-c)} \right]^{m-n-1} V_{m-n-1}(f_m, t, f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}, \dots, f_{m-1} \dots) \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

The ratio test together with 3.2 and 3.3, implies that the series converges and thus the sequence $\{f_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a Cauchy sequence. Since (Z, d) is complete controlled metric space there exists $f^* \in Z$ such that

$$d(f_n, f^*, t) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Proving f^* is a fixed point. Using (3.6) we get

$$\begin{aligned} d(f^*, Hf^*, t) &\leq \alpha(f^*, Hf^*, f_{n+1}) d(f^*, Hf^*, f_{n+1}) \\ &\quad + \beta(Hf^*, t, f_{n+1}) d(Hf^*, t, Hf^*, f_{n+1}) + \gamma(t, f^*, f_{n+1}) d(t, f^*, f_{n+1}) \\ &\leq \alpha(f^*, Hf^*, f_{n+1}) d(f^*, Hf^*, f_{n+1}) + \beta(Hf^*, t, f_{n+1}) d(Hf^*, t, Hf_n) \\ &\quad + \gamma(t, f^*, f_{n+1}) d(t, f^*, f_{n+1}) \\ &\leq \alpha(f^*, Hf^*, f_{n+1}) d(f^*, Hf^*, f_{n+1}) + \beta(Hf^*, t, f_{n+1}) kd(f^*, t, f_n) \\ &\quad + \gamma(t, f^*, f_{n+1}) d(t, f^*, f_{n+1}). \end{aligned}$$

Taking the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and using (3.6), we get

$$d(f^*, Hf^*, t) \leq 0.$$

Implies, $Hf^* = f^*$.

Uniqueness:

Suppose there is another fixed point $f^{**} \neq f^*$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (3.10) \quad d(f^*, f^{**}, t) &= d(Hf^*, Hf^{**}, t) \leq (\mathfrak{L}(f^*) - \mathfrak{L}(f^{**})) d(f^*, f^{**}, t) \\ d(f^*, f^{**}, t) &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

which implies $f^* = f^{**}$. Thus the mapping H has a unique fixed point $f^* \in Z$.

Remarks:

1. In case, $b = c = 0$, we get result due to Theorem 2.5 of [5].
2. In case, $a = 0$ and $b = c$, we get result due to Theorem 2.6 of [5].

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